

The Implications of Minority Women Lacking Nursing Leadership Positions

Capstone Proposal

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Abstract

This mixed-methods, qualitative, and quantitative research study aims to identify if Minority women in health services, such as nursing, have faced many challenges and how overcoming diversity has positively impacted their advancement in healthcare. Barriers such as pay gaps, lack of mentorship, discrimination, doctor-to-patient relationships, and organizational culture continue to remain a burden for minority women in nursing leadership positions, such as hospitals. Underrepresentation has become a massive issue with Minority women in nursing leadership positions, often making it harder for them to secure leadership roles (Scholar Works, S., & Jones, M., 2023). As many of these challenges remain prevalent today, minority woman in nursing leadership positions continues to fight for equality and their rights to be successful in the nursing healthcare industry (Lorioswald, 2023).

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Introductions

Dating back to the early 1950s and 1960s, minority women have been fighting for equality to achieve their career goals in the nursing healthcare industry (NBNA, 2024). Many challenges minority women in nursing leadership positions face include discrimination and other factors in the workplace, such as a lack of career advancement roles. Having a diverse culture in hospitals is vital in healthcare organizations and hospitals. According to Dunkley (2024), fewer minority women occupy nursing leadership positions. Unfortunately, fewer minority women advance to executive nursing leadership positions (2004).

Creating organizations such as the National Black Nurses Association helped create Minority women in nursing leadership roles who have broken racial barriers and inspired many generations of minority women nurses to pursue careers in healthcare leadership roles in hospital settings (Meneses, 2025). The prevalence of Minority women in nursing leadership roles remains a sensitive topic due to discrimination. These challenges can lead to disparities, causing minority women to fail to achieve their nursing leadership positions (Iheduru-Anderson, 2020). Although challenges arrive in the healthcare field for minority women in nursing leadership positions, pushing through barriers and achieving nursing goals are enormous achievements for minority women in nursing leadership positions.

Problem Statement

The problem that is to be evaluated in this study is to show how minority women are often underrepresented in nursing leadership positions in hospital settings. According to (Suarez C, 2023), this unethical issue has been going on for centuries. Minority women lack nursing leadership positions for many reasons besides their qualifications. Over time, minority women fought for justice by overcoming barriers to their right to remain prevalent in the healthcare workplace. Lack of healthcare leadership roles for minority women also causes minority women to be forced out of positions or are often exhausted to where they must resign from them or step down from certain leadership positions. The lack of support, resources, and infrastructure needed to thrive is often nonexistent in some workplace practices (Suarez, C, 2023). These factors have been in place for years and have not entirely changed. Fighting for justice helped minority women in nursing leadership roles reduce health disparities in hospitals and other healthcare settings and fight for their right to have equal career opportunities (Iheduru-Anderson, K. 2020).

According to AONL, 2021, diverse nurse leaders often experience unequal access to opportunities, a lack of mentors, and little to no sponsorships and leadership experience opportunities. There are limited career opportunities for implementing nursing leadership positions, which also include public practices, private practices, and many other healthcare sectors in healthcare practices. These positions range from certified nursing positions, licensed practical nursing, registered nursing, director of nursing, healthcare administrator, and other leadership positions that minority women would like to work in within hospital settings. The lack of leadership roles is limited for minority women due to their ethnicity, gender, and race (Iheduru-Anderson, K., Okoro, F. O., & Moore, S. S, 2022). This creates workplace barriers for minority women. Creating challenging spaces for minority women, such as wage gaps, growth,

and healthy work environments. Other factors include a lack of patience to build relationships. Due to this unprecedented issue, the lack of implementation of minority women in nursing leadership roles is limited for many urban communities in hospital settings. Minority women account for 20 percent of entry-level healthcare leadership positions, such as nursing, but only 5 percent of c-suite leadership positions (Stewart, 2021). Due to this factor, minority patients may have trust issues with specific providers. There are many unhealthy practices that Minority women go through in their careers in nursing leadership positions. Due to these reasons, there continues to be a lack of nursing leadership positions in hospital settings for Minority women, Stewart, M (2021, April 19).

Purpose of Research

The purpose of this mixed-method research study is to examine how, if at all, minority women in nursing leadership roles often lack nursing positions. Challenges such as structured barriers, housing segregation, and economic instability and growth have caused significant challenges to Minority women pursuing nursing leadership positions, degrees, and careers (Bajaj, S. S., Tu, L., & Stanford, F. C., 2021), both a qualitative and quantitative approach. The purpose of this study is to discover and research why the lack of positions for minority women in healthcare leadership roles continues to create hardship for minority women in leadership positions, as well as in leadership positions. The study is intended to provide insight into how minority women are overcoming barriers and hardships to be implemented into leadership positions due to their credentials and education, and not ethnicity. Participants will be provided with survey questions for the interviewer to conduct.

Literature Review

History of Challenges in Healthcare

Historically, minority women in nursing leadership roles have faced significant underrepresentation and systematic barriers, a struggle that lasted for centuries. The root of this inequality traces back to the era of slavery, when minority women mainly practiced nursing on plantations (History of Diversity and Inclusivity in Nursing HPU Online, 2023, August). They provided care for enslaved individuals and occasionally for plantation owners and their families. Although minority women gained extensive practical experience, they were excluded from professional education settings and practical experiences.

Following the Civil War, the demand for nurses surged, and the Civil War was in demand for nurses. When hiring minority women (black nurses), black nurses were segregated. In contrast, white nurses were prioritized for hiring instead of education and experience (History of Diversity and Inclusivity in Nursing HPU Online, 2023, August). Meanwhile, minority women in nursing positions were denied access to decision-making policies, which perpetuated racial inequalities in healthcare experiences (History of Diversity and Inclusivity in Nursing HPU Online, 2023, August). Implementing minority women nurses in hospitals came about in 1964 when the Civil Rights Act was passed. As time progressed, minority women in nursing leadership roles continued to fight for equality of being implemented in the nursing field.

Minority women in nursing leadership positions have been pushing forward to prove they belong in the nursing industry. Historically, it has been challenging for minority women in nursing leadership roles to achieve career and advancement opportunities. These issues have

arisen for centuries now, causing a lack of diversity and equality in hospitals and other healthcare settings (Pincha, Garth, Boyd, Ward, Joseph, Proimos, & Teede, 2023).

Influences of Early Minority Nursing Leaders

Pioneers like Dr. Betty Smith Williams and Barbara Johnson often discussed improving the healthcare system. While discussing and advocating for minority women nursing leaders to be implemented into healthcare practices, such as hospitals. This led to Black Women in leadership roles forming the National Black Nurses Association. As the article mentioned, black nurse leaders such as Dr. Betty Smith Williams and Barbara Johnson helped hospitals and nursing settings develop diverse nursing institutions. This helped create an equitable environment for minority women in nursing leadership roles. These trailblazers understood that the exclusion of minority women from leadership roles not only harmed the nurses themselves but also perpetuated broader racial disparities within the healthcare system (History of Diversity and Inclusivity in Nursing HPU Online, 2023, August). Although they had overcome barriers, they continued to fight for minority women in nursing roles (Iheduru-Anderson, K, 2020)

Throughout history, minority women have paved the way for implementing nursing leadership roles. Although Title VII of the Civil Rights Act of 1964 was passed to protect employees and applicants from discrimination based on race, color, religion, or national origin, laws such as the dismantling of the DEI (diversity, equality, and inclusion act) by President Donald J. Trump, puts this policy to end (Murray, C., & Bohannon, M. 2025). Many minority women are faced with the obstacles that other minority women in nursing work for to be treated fairly and equally. Historically, these factors made it harder for minority women to achieve nursing leadership roles. In today's society, it remains a tough factor due to the lack of advocacy

for minority women. President Trump signed an executive order that anyone who refuses to abide by the dismantling of the DEI will face consequences (Business, E, 2025).

Lack of leadership positions for Minority Nurses

In hospital settings, minority nurses in healthcare leadership roles face a lack of leadership positions. According to the article: *Outsiders Within: The Live Experience of Being Black and Female When Becoming a Nurse Executive* (Dunkley, D., .2024), few minority women occupy leadership roles, and even fewer will advance to careers as nursing executives. These issues are due to the lack of mentorship, pay gaps, discrimination, and the lack of diversity in hospital settings for minority nurses wanting to advance in leadership positions. If any, minority women find it more difficult to advance in leadership roles due to these circumstances.

In the article, *Outsiders Within: The Live Experience of Being Black and Female When Becoming a Nurse Executive* (Dunkley, D, .2024), a hermeneutic phenomenological method was conducted to explore the lived experiences of minority nurses on being black and female and becoming a nurse executive and the experience between being black and female. The experience sampled 10 minority female nurses through telephone interviews. The article further explained disparities such as gender, race, and class discrimination while managing their nursing career leadership positions. The study that was conducted was intended to discuss the results of the research study that was conducted and how it will help nursing healthcare executives and related professionals understand the experience of minority women in nursing leadership roles and how increasing minority representation can improve health equality in healthcare settings (Dunkley, D., 2024).

While examining the study, the study focused on how minority women in healthcare leadership roles are often not implemented due to the lack of diversity in hospital settings. Advocating for equality, mentorship, and driving research has helped minority women in nursing leadership roles advance in healthcare leadership roles. Overcoming these barriers negatively impacts minority women in nursing positions in many ways. Leading to self-doubt and burnout in the workforce.

Challenges Minority Women Experience

Minority women in nursing leadership roles are often faced with many challenges. When considering entering leadership roles, minority women are faced with a lack of mentorship, economic and financial challenges, and a lack of ability to get hired in some hiring facilities due to their ethnicity. According to (Nelson, Y. M., Bundy, J., Harmon, E., Hammond, L., Robinson, K., Lyons, N., Vessels, R., Bush, K., & Thomas-Payne, D. 2023) nurses of color represent only 20 percent of leadership roles which include administration, nursing administration and education. Due to a lack of representation of minority women in leadership, barriers continue to rise in healthcare facilities.

Unfair hiring practices create challenges for minority women nurses in leadership roles. This can lead to minority women in nursing feeling micromanaged as well as receiving insults or stereotyped (Pinnix, K. 2024). These factors can lead to minority women nurses feeling mentally drained and burnt out. Due to these factors, minority women nurses, if any, feel disheartened or like a setback in their careers. These concerns can cause minority woman in nursing leadership roles to resign or step down from their leadership positions.

According to Jean, J. 2023), statistically, the higher a minority woman is in upper leadership roles, the less likely they are to see another minority woman in leadership roles just like them.

Due to this, minority women, if any, may believe leadership roles are not for them or become out of reach to them because of their ethnicity. Due to the lack of implementation of minority nurses into leadership roles, management may not consider minority women for leadership positions due to their own bias against minority women (Jean, J. 2023).

Examining Wage Disparities

Wage gaps are an ongoing issue with Minority women nurses in healthcare leadership positions or seeking healthcare leadership positions. According to the article: Examining Wage Disparities by Race and Ethnicity of Health Care Workers (Frogner, B.K., & Schwartz, M., 2021), ethnic discrimination has played a part in wage gaps, organizational culture discrimination, and healthcare disparities. The article examines how careers as CNAs, nurses, and other healthcare workers are often compensated with low wages due to their ethnicity. The article analyzes that minorities are frequently portrayed as less than other ethnicities, such as Latinos and Asian ethnicities. Statistically, the article provides tables to explain how barriers are created for minority women, so it harder for minority women to achieve more.

Wage gaps are convenient for all genders, ethnicities, and experience levels. However, minority women are impacted the most, especially in leadership positions. The article examines how these effects continue to hurt minority women's wealth and the impact it has on minority women to provide for their families as well as their livelihood. This leaves fewer minority women positions, which causes disparities for minority patients who request minority healthcare providers. Due to wage gaps for minority women nurses in healthcare leadership, any minority women in healthcare leadership are left with the burden of maintaining their lifestyle for themselves or their families causing financial hardships (Loftin, C., Newman, S. D., Dumas, B. P., Gilden, G., & Bond, M. L, 2012).

According to (Nurse Journal 2021), Minority women nurses in leadership pay gaps are likely to close slowly than those of other genders and ethnicities. The gender wage gap has impacted both Latina and Black women nurses, with an earnings ratio of 59% and rising to 63% in the last 30 years (Nurse Journal, 2021, June). When it comes to salary, minority women, if at all, are paid lower salaries. The reasons are often based on discrimination factors, gender factors, or underrepresentation (Loftin, C., Newman, S. D., Dumas, B. P., Gilden, G., & Bond, M. L. 2012).

Minority women in Nursing leadership Turnover

Minority women in nursing leadership positions often experience a higher turnover rate. This leads to employee burnout and job dissatisfaction, causing minority women in nursing to step down from leadership positions or reign. According to (Stewart, M. 2021, April), higher turnover rates, including disparities in job satisfaction, perceived discrimination, and limited opportunities for advancement, can lead to burnout and a desire to leave (Brooks, M., Nikpour, J., Rettberg, G., Thomas-Hawkins, C., Henderson, M. D., Agor, D., & Villarruel, A, 2024)

Due to the lack of opportunities and resources, this leads to barriers for minority women seeking nursing leadership positions and opportunities in hospitals and other healthcare settings.

Moreover, unequal career advancement opportunities exacerbate the high turnover rate among minority women in nursing leadership. Implicit bias in hiring and promoting processes often prevent qualified candidates from securing leadership roles, creating a cycle in which minority women in nursing leadership positions remain underrepresented in executive and managerial positions (Brooke et al.,2024). Without equitable access to promotions, leadership training, and other related factors. Many minority women in nursing leadership positions find themselves stagnant in their careers, prompting them to seek other positions.

Organizational Culture and DEI

Organizational culture remains a challenging and ongoing issue for minority nurses in leadership roles. According to the American Nurses Association (2023), a survey of over 5,600 nurses (63 % of the study) found that they had personally experienced racism in the workplace. These factors analyzed how racism in organizations affected nurses mentally. Racism affected Minority nurses, which affected communities, patients, and healthcare systems (American Nurses Association, 2023). Due to these ongoing factors, cultural diversity remains limited.

Hospitals and other organizations that have developed DEI (diversity, equity, and inclusion) programs have created programs to help reshape cultural approaches and diversify their organizations (Williams, M., Dubree, M., & Schorn, M. N. 2025). DEI programs help healthcare organizations address cultural diversity and the lack of diversity in healthcare organizations and hospitals. Unfortunately, there remains a burden in the healthcare system that overrides DEI Programs. As of 2025, President Donald Trump initiated a ban on DEI programs causing a sweeping effect on the healthcare system (Beavins, E, 2025). Banning DEI programs impacts equal opportunities for Minority Nurses in leadership roles, causing a lack of diversity in healthcare practices and hospitals. Banning programs like the DEI programs create disparities in healthcare settings, as well as minority communities.

Banning DEI initiative programs has an enormous impact on minority women in healthcare leadership positions in the future. Plans such as DEI funding, programs, and diversity training, remain a setback in education for minority women (Bettencourt, E. 2025). Policies and procedures have changed the dynamic of DEI initiative programs as well as cutting funding on future programs needed to achieve success for minorities (Bettencourt, E. 2025). In the meantime, minority women in nursing positions can take actionable steps to advance working

through the DEI initiative ban. According to *A Nurse's Call to Action: Supporting DEI in Healthcare* (Bettencourt, E. 2025), firstly, educating others as well as self about disparities and culture competence. Secondly, advocating for policy change and supporting legislation to promote equality. Third, engaging in mentorship and representation, uplifting underrepresented voices by mentoring Nursing students and providers. Fourth, fostering inclusive Work Environments encourages a culture of respect and understanding in workplaces. Lastly, speaking up for patients, and recognizing and addressing implicit biases in patient care.

Patient-to-Provider Relationship

Building strong patient-provider relationships in the nursing industry is crucial. Minority women in nursing leadership roles are faced with challenges in patient-provider relationships. Minority women in healthcare leadership roles may experience discriminatory behaviors from patients and their families. Overall, enduring discriminatory issues and problems cause emotional distress and lead to employee burnout (Yung, A., Ishmael, T. G., Llanes, A. C., & Belthur, M. V. 2023). Cultural differences also play a critical role in minority women in the nursing leadership role, leading to cultural differences in how patients interact with minority providers in nursing.

However, minority patients may have a different perspective on minority women in nursing leadership positions. This can be exceptionally important for minority women in nursing leadership positions in hospital settings because minority patients often mistrust, lack communication, and experience other healthcare disparities. With other providers of different ethnicities (Adams, V., & Craddock, J., 2023). These factors contribute to young black women having to convince healthcare providers to receive the necessary services or medical treatment they need. The minority population is often influenced by medical beliefs that shape the

healthcare system, which may not particularly meet their standards with other providers (Adams, V., & Craddock, J., 2023).

Minority Nursing Leaders Shaping the Future of Healthcare

Career advancements for minority women in nursing leadership positions continue to be lacking for many reasons. Minority women in nursing leadership positions are still overcoming barriers to earning their right to belong in the nursing field. The article: Career Advancement of Black Nurses in Healthcare: The Lived Experience of Successful Leaders and Critical Elements Along the Way (Yancey, 2018) used a theoretical framework and face-to-face semi-structured interviews to find that black female nurses are if at all, underrepresented at the leadership level of healthcare finding their right to belong (Yancey, P., 2018). The study suggested that black nurses must ensure that expanding diverse patient populations helps them achieve leadership positions. Black women, if at all, faced obstacles such as underrepresentation while still pursuing their career goals. Implementing minority women nurses in healthcare leadership roles has shaped healthcare settings in many positive ways. According to The Role of Nurses in Promoting Diversity & Inclusion in Healthcare (Jordan, A. 2023), these reasons include improving patient care and implementing a diverse workforce. Enhancing communication and collaboration and implementing diversity leads to better communication within the healthcare system. Minority women in nursing leadership roles can address health disparities in the healthcare system. Advocating policies and practices that address healthcare diversity and help improve access to care. Implementing these healthcare methods helps positively shape the future of minority women in healthcare leadership roles.

Minority women nurses in leadership roles are shaping the future in many ways. For example, the article explains that advocating for equality, mentorship, and driving research has

helped minority women in nursing leadership roles advance in healthcare leadership roles in healthcare settings. The article further explains that minority women in healthcare leadership roles, if any, contribute diverse perspectives to improve patient care and reduce health disparities (Hewitt, R. 2025, February 3). Creating resources is especially important in diverse communities, as it helps with overcoming health disparities.

Minority women in nursing leadership roles are advocates for urban communities, which do not receive adequate resources as other communities. Minority women in nursing leadership roles may advocate for policy change in communities and reach out to legislators to present policy changes to them (Flauber, Menestrel, Williams, & Wakefield, 2021). Additionally, organizations such as the National Black Nurses Association can advocate for Minority women nurses as well as diverse populations. Providing resources such as health education and screenings to diverse communities allows community-based partners, including hospitals and other healthcare organizations, to have the necessary resources and education they need to support diverse communities in need (MBNA., 2025). Minority women nurse leaders can help improve health outcomes for minority patients and serve as voices for minority patients in decision-making processes (Johnson & Johnson, 2021). Engaging in community outreach programs, such as volunteering to provide adequate resources to diverse communities, can expand healthcare access as well as empower communities to work together to meet their needs, but it does not provide resources that diverse communities may need but do not know about (Lashley, M. 2024).

Research Questions

The purpose of this mixed-method research study is to examine how, if at all, minority women in nursing leadership roles often lack nursing positions. Challenges such as structured barriers, housing segregation, and economic instability and growth have caused significant challenges to Minority women pursuing nursing leadership positions, degrees, and careers (Bajaj, S. S., Tu, L., & Stanford, F. C., 2021) will be examined.

RQ1:

Can nursing departments change their approach and culture to address the recruitment, retention, advancement problems, and concerns of underrepresented minority women?

RQ2:

Are there any interpersonal differences between coworkers, supervisors, and minority nurses advancing with career opportunities and promotional advancement in the healthcare industry?

Research Methods

Research Methodology

This study focuses on a mixed method using qualitative and quantitative approaches to examine minority women in nursing leadership positions and their viewpoints on discrimination, wage and salary discrimination, workplace bias, career advancement, and social barriers. The study used both qualitative and quantitative research methods to collect data and present the results of the data. In the study, researchers, as well as participants, conducted research work closely to come to a shared understanding of participants' experiences (Creswell J. W., Poth C. N. 2017). In the study, collecting information from participants, such as statistical data, and various research methods, is to be examined.

Study Population and Sampling Procedure

The population examined used a mixed method that used non-managerial minority women in nursing, including both leadership positions and non-leadership roles. The study's geographic location will focus on the Philadelphia area. This study population included minority women in healthcare leadership roles who relate to the concepts in the research study. This population was targeted due to their correlation and personal experiences that they may have faced in hospital settings. The study population included minority women in healthcare leadership roles, including minority registered nurses and minority licensed practical nurses in management and leadership. The study conducted a probability sampling process, which included random sampling selection. Participants were asked to participate by using online recruitment options on social media platforms. 21 participants engaged in this research study (See appendix).

Results and findings

In the research study, fifteen participants were asked to answer a series of questions and provide their feedback, however, additional participants were sent the survey, and 21 participants responded. These questions examined minority women in nursing leadership roles and their viewpoints on wage and salary discrimination, workplace bias, career advancement, and social barriers. Participants were asked questions based on two research questions that were being analyzed (See appendix). While analyzing the data for the questions, a qualitative analysis of the comment section in the survey, where participants had to write in their answers to comment on their experiences (see appendix). The quantitative approach was used to determine the findings by using a scale to evaluate the percentages and numerical data. These findings represented the data collected from the participants and their experiences.

In the survey, participants were given questions to review and provide their feedback using a scale. Participants were asked to rate their experience from one to ten. One is slightly impacted by 10, which has a huge impact on their experience. Participants were asked to provide their feedback and experience in a comment box in the survey where half of the women provided insight about their experience (see appendix). In the pie charts below, there were four questions asked, and the percentages represent the number of minority women in nursing leadership positions and how their experiences were rated using the scale that was provided in the survey. The questions below were collected in the survey that participants received to participate:

Can healthcare organizations better support minority women in nursing leadership positions?

You felt you needed to work harder to exceed your organization's expectations than your majority counterparts?

Do you believe you have experienced barriers to career advancement due to your ethnicity/race or gender? If so, please describe.

What, if any, were the biggest challenges you have faced when pursuing your leadership role

Implications Of the Results and Findings

While examining the results and findings of the data in the survey on The Implications of Minority Women Lacking Nursing Leadership Positions, there were several key findings to analyze. Findings such as career advancement were considered when analyzing the results for minority women in healthcare leadership roles. The survey was able to display a scale that represented how minority women in healthcare leadership roles felt about their experiences in their leadership role, and allowed the comment box to explain their feelings about the experience. Analyzing the scale and data on the findings displayed the factors that minority women in nursing leadership roles were able to tell their perspective on how they could be implemented in minority women leadership positions that are lacking in the nursing field.

When researching the topic there were several factors to learn from and take into consideration. The lack of diversity and discrimination played a factor in how minority women in leadership are lacking leadership positions. When conducting the survey, many minority women in nursing expressed that this was the biggest issue for them in the nursing field. In the comment section of the survey, minority women shared their experience of how discrimination played a part in how their counterparts often felt that they did not belong in their nursing leadership positions. Minority women in the study felt that they were not supported in the healthcare field. There were 5% of minority women who reported that they feel like healthcare organizations do not have to support minority women in nursing leadership positions, and 94 % of minority women felt that minority women in nursing leadership positions could be supported more in healthcare organizations. In the survey, 81% of minority women felt like they had to work harder than their counterparts had to work in nursing leadership roles, and 19% felt like they did not have to work as hard as their counterparts did. The minority women in the survey

said to have experienced these issues due to their ethnicity and gender, and attributed that factor to working harder and continuing to lack leadership roles due to these issues. However, 14 % of minority women in nursing leadership revealed that they have not experienced any barriers or lack of career advancement roles, and 14 % revealed that sometimes they feel like they must work harder. 72 % of minority women in nursing leadership roles revealed that there were barriers that played a part in why they did not advance in their careers. The survey revealed that 71% of minority women in nursing are faced with big challenges to overcome. 2 % of women said no, and 4 % of women said sometimes they experience bigger challenges due to their ethnicity and/or gender.

The results implied that a vast majority of minority women in nursing leadership positions experience challenges in healthcare organizations. According to the survey, more minority women acknowledged the lack of leadership roles due to not being considered for certain positions or having to overcome hurdles because of their skin color, and not their work ethic or job position. The results of the survey provided congruence with the results of available research. The percentages of minority women in nursing leadership positions were often at a higher percentage rate, as minority women in nursing leadership experienced discrimination at a higher rate. Minority women often felt that overcoming barriers for minority women is more prominent than for other races or genders. The results aligned with other findings and perspectives on the impact of minority women in nursing leadership experience. Some of these are included in the findings in the reference page that were researched in the study (see appendix).

Applying the findings to the professional practice of organizational leadership and management regarding minority women in nursing leadership positions can potentially lead to many other factors. These factors include addressing implicit bias, providing mentorship and networking

opportunities for minority women, and ensuring fair and adequate pay options (Shen, Q., Tucker, S, 2024). Applying these findings helps with promoting diversity and Inclusion and continues to help minority women in nursing leadership positions advocate for change. Community engagement creates opportunities for minority nurses in leadership roles to bridge the gap between healthcare organizations and communities. Applying these findings helps achieve goals for professional organizational leadership and management, creates change, and helps minority women overcome barriers in the healthcare system. Companies and organizations may take the available data and research, learn from it, and improve in many ways. This data and research provide insight into creating supported work environments for minority women in nursing leadership positions. Creating mentorship and sponsorship programs helps connect minority women in nursing to other connections and programs that can provide more opportunities. Organizations and companies can take the data from the research study and consider it in their hiring process. Improving recruitment and hiring processes to seek out minority women in nursing leadership roles is beneficial and creates equal opportunities (Khuntia J, Ning X, Cascio W, Stacey R, 2021). Companies and organizations can also take leadership accountability within healthcare organizations. When organizations within healthcare leadership hold leaders accountable, clearer goals and vision could be set to provide equality within the healthcare system for minority women in nursing leadership positions. Future research can provide educational resources on minority women in nursing leadership by providing insight into the impact and diversity. Researching minority women in nursing leadership roles and education organizations can influence future workplace cultures, organizational effectiveness, patient outcomes, and future experience. Future research can encourage cultural competencies and allow minority women in nursing leadership roles to contribute to healthcare education and provide

insight on how to effectively provide education competencies and unique leadership styles amongst other organizations that are struggling to implement diversity into their healthcare organizations. Other suggestions such as allowing minority women in nursing leadership roles to be able to provide their narratives. Learning from experiences and other minority women in nursing leadership stories on discrimination, workplace bias, wage differences, and other stories, including their barriers, helps educate healthcare organizations to learn not to accept anything that will create barriers and difficulties with any healthcare workers in their organizations. Hearing personal experiences and narratives on challenges and success stories could serve as an inspiration and can help guide other minority women in nursing and create inspiration for future leaders.

Limitations Of the Study

In the study, the extenuating circumstances that limit the data collection or study in general are challenges in gaining more participants. Although the study contained more participants than anticipated, some participants were harder to access due to scheduling conflicts or were afraid or hesitant to broadcast their experiences. Other extenuating circumstances included limited data for using the number scale. Most participants used the scale, while other participants only wrote their experience in the comment section, leaving minimal data to go off of in the study. Other factors included some minority women refusing to answer the questions as they did not feel the need to do so, as they wanted to get the study done with. This extenuating circumstance provided the study with limited data that could have helped the study statistically. Due to the lack of data, the study provided limited data that could have been helpful if the study had contained more participants.

Conclusion

In summation, the purpose of this mix of minority women in nursing leadership positions. Although studies have been conducted on the Implications of Minority women Lacking Nursing Leadership Positions in Hospital Settings, very few research studies have been conducted on minority women's experiences, challenges, and barriers. According to the literature review, minority women in healthcare leadership roles experienced hardship for decades and navigating through these barriers helped shape the healthcare system in positive ways for minorities (Dias, Joseph, & Michael, 2019). Moreover, this study revealed experiences and feedback on the lack of positions and opportunities in healthcare settings and the barriers and lack of opportunities they have endured on their journey in the nursing industry.

According to Iheduru-Anderson (2023), historically, minority women in nursing leadership roles lacked nursing positions for centuries. Minority women in nursing leadership fought for the right to be included in the healthcare system. Minority women were faced with factors including limited resources and limited funding for nursing school. Although minority women fought hard to fight for equality in the nursing leadership field, there continue to be barriers that prevent minority women in nursing leadership from achieving their future leadership goals. The problem in the study is that minority women in nursing leadership positions experience barriers, including being underrepresented based on discrimination measures, workplace biases, wage differences, and other factors due to race and gender. According to the study of minority women in nursing leadership positions, these problems and factors are often lacking due to factors other than their qualifications in the nursing industry.

According to Rosseter R. (2023), although the outcome for minority women in nursing leadership positions is an ongoing fight for minority women. Minority women in healthcare

leadership can educate communities and other healthcare professionals and facilities on implementing them into the healthcare system. The lack of employee resignation continues to be an issue for minority women. This leads to a lack of promotion, an increase and pay wages, and a lack of diversity in the workplace. Although there have been some changes for minority women in the workplace, programs such as overturning DEI initiative programs create an insecure healthcare system for minority women in healthcare leadership positions. The next future steps for minority women in nursing leadership positions are creating programs and organizations that are seen in healthcare facilities. Minority women may encourage and foster mentorship programs for other minority women in nursing. Creating these programs can impact other healthcare facilities to educate and learn more about culture and implementing diversity. In the future, minority women in nursing can address pay disparities more openly with employers to encourage employers to close the pay gaps within gender and race. Future steps may also include minority leaders fighting for anti-racism and equality for gender training in the workplace.

According to Mattison M. 2022, minority women in nursing leadership roles fought for many years. Despite overcoming barriers, minority women in leadership continue to thrive. Educating underrepresented communities and educating others on how to implement minority women in nursing leadership positions allowed minority women to create different systems and programs to educate communities and facilities. Minority women can present policies to politicians, advocate for change, and challenge racial bias in healthcare facilities. The future of minority women in nursing leadership is promising with the support of healthcare facilities and the implementation of policies and programs to help minority women in nursing leadership positions continue to thrive and become successful. This study aims to provide awareness for minority women in nursing leadership positions. Implementing diversity and programs to help minority

women in healthcare leadership positions is exceptionally important as it creates opportunities for minority women in healthcare leadership to perform their job duties as other genders and ethnicities can. Minority women in nursing leadership positions deserve to be treated fairly and equally, and respectfully as they perform their nursing leadership positions.

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Appendix A

While conducting the study, two research questions were analyzed to gather information. The questions help examine research information to conduct the research study.

RQ1:

Can nursing departments change their approach and culture to address the recruitment, retention, advancement problems, and concerns of underrepresented minority women?

RQ2:

Are there any interpersonal differences between coworkers, supervisors, and minority nurses advancing with career opportunities and promotional advancement in the healthcare industry?

Appendix B

Survey Questions

The applicable items in the appendix will provide an overview of questions that will be conducted in the research study. Participants are expected to be asked these questions in this study for research purposes.

1. Can healthcare organizations better support minority women in healthcare leadership positions?
2. Have you felt you needed to work harder to exceed your organization's expectations than your majority-race/gender counterparts?
3. Do you believe you have experienced barriers to career advancement due to your ethnicity/race or gender? If so, please describe.
4. What, if any, were the biggest challenges you have faced when pursuing your leadership role?

Appendix C

In the survey, fifteen participants were asked to participate in the research study for The Implications of Minority Women Lacking Nursing Leadership Positions. Although fifteen participants were asked to participate, an additional eight participants agreed to take part in the study. In the survey, minority women were asked to give feedback in a comment box. The following questions were asked, and some participants replied to the questions:

Q1: Can healthcare organizations better support minority women in nursing leadership positions?

Participant 1: Yes! Minority women in nursing leadership positions can be supported more.

Participant 2: Absolutely! Will they be the big question?

Participant 3: Most definitely!!

Q2: Have you felt you needed to work harder to exceed your organization's expectations than your majority-race/gender counterparts?

Participant 1: Yes, gender and race play a major role in exceeding and having a successful organization.

Participant 2: I agree. It could be hard

Participant 3: Absolutely!

Q3: Do you believe you have experienced barriers to career advancement due to your ethnicity/race or gender? If so, please describe

Participant 1: Yes. For example, as an African American Nurse. I gave challenges daily. From the data I collect during Nursing Assessments, I can advance in my career.

Participant 2: Being black in the healthcare field can be very discriminatory and difficult to succeed.

Participant 3: Yes, unequal access to sponsorship

What, if any, were the biggest challenges you have faced when pursuing your leadership role?

Participant 1: I have once called a rare medical condition. Based on the signs and symptoms that the patient was experiencing. However, my diagnosis was not taken seriously, not because I was not correct, but because of my skin color. Hours later, a white counterpart came on and said the same diagnosis that I had mentioned earlier, and it was like I never had said it. The team agreed with her and ran a test. It was unfortunate as I had mentioned the same diagnosis. Hours ago. But my findings were dismissed. At that moment, I realized racism still exists.

Participant 2: Caucasian clients do not want to deal with minorities in leadership positions.

Participant 3: Being Judged a Lot Because I am African American Working as a Nurse. Patients think I do not know how to do my job.

